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RESEARCH PAPER

AWARENESS OF PENILE OSSIFICATION AMONG MEN: A PILOT EXPLORATORY CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Penile ossification is a rare condition characterized by bone formation within the penis, often associated with Peyronie's disease, trauma, or chronic inflammation; however, awareness of this condition among men remains largely unknown. This study aimed to assess awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking intentions regarding penile ossification among Nigerian men. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 262 predominantly young, educated men using a structured self-administered questionnaire, which collected sociodemographic data, awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking behaviors. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings, and ethical approval was obtained with informed consent from all participants. Results indicated that while 73.8% of respondents were aware of general penile health conditions, only 26.7% had heard of penile ossification. Approximately 47.1% correctly distinguished it from an erection, whereas 41.3% were uncertain. Most respondents (86.1%) expressed willingness to learn more about the condition, and 95.0% indicated they would recommend hospital consultation for unusual penile changes. Although 12.7% of the respondents believed that spiritual or traditional interventions may be required, a majority disagreed (58.7%). Overall, awareness of penile ossification among Nigerian men is limited, despite positive attitudes toward biomedical care, highlighting the need for targeted educational interventions to improve knowledge, correct misconceptions, and promote timely health-seeking behavior.

Keywords: Penile ossification, Peyronie's disease, awareness, health-seeking behavior, sexual health, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Sexual and reproductive health literacy is integral to overall health promotion, particularly among young adults developing lifelong health behaviors (Muehlmann *et al.*, 2025). Most sexual health education and public health interventions emphasise the usual conditions (e.g., sexually transmitted infections, contraception, puberty), thus hardly providing any mention of the rarer penile conditions, which can have serious functional, psychological and quality of life implications (Castleton *et al.*, 2024).

One of these unusual physical entities is penile ossification, which is the formation of bone tissue within the soft tissues of the penis. Rarely, but found in association with metaplastic changes related to Peyronie's disease, penile trauma, chronic inflammation, or systemic disorders, penile ossification is associated with the curvature, pain, and erectile dysfunction seen when ossified plaques appear in corpora cavernosa (Belshoff *et al.*, 2021; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2013; El Hasbani *et al.*, 2019; Vahlensieck *et al.*, 1995).

Although there is a high clinical importance for penile ossification, it is rarely studied in sexual health instruction and public awareness, perceptions, and intentions to pursue medical care concerning this phenomenon are sparse. This lack of knowledge can lead to health-behaviour implications: individuals who are unfamiliar with atypical penile disorders might be less likely to identify symptoms, understand the symptoms and to seek prompt professional treatment. Studies of sexual health literacy reveal that knowledge deficiencies remain for young educated adults over less-revised or less-explored sexual health topics and this inadequacy is shown to be linked to reduced confidence in health care of related matters (Muehlmann *et al.*, 2025; Castleton *et al.*, 2024).

Moreover, cultural beliefs and interpretation tend to overlap and interact with biomedical knowledge in ways that influence the way individuals view and respond to health problems. Evidence from reproductive and sexual well-being has highlighted that other theoretical interpretations, such as traditional or spiritual explanations, could be influential in the choice of the care decision, and may in some cases postpone referral to the formal health system (Bekman *et al.*, 2023). Understanding these perception patterns is vital for creating impactful strategies for health communication and education campaigns targeted at the youth that meet their needs while being culturally appropriate.

A key challenge is paucity of literature in this area, as no study has specifically investigated awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking behaviours regarding penile ossification among non-specific youth samples or within broader studies of awareness of common sexual health conditions. Addressing this gap is important given the functional implications of the condition and the role of health literacy in promoting timely care. Accordingly, this study evaluates the awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking intentions related to penile ossification among a population predominantly composed of young, educated Nigerian men.

METHODS

Study Design: This exploratory study employed a cross-sectional design to assess awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking intentions regarding penile ossification among young male adults. A cross-sectional approach was deemed appropriate for capturing the prevalence of awareness and perceptions at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of knowledge and attitudes within the target population (Levin, 2006).

Study Population and Sampling: The study population comprised predominantly young adults enrolled in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Participants were selected using the convenience sampling technique, targeting students and young professionals who were accessible and willing to participate. A total of 262 respondents completed the study questionnaire, forming the final analytic sample. Inclusion criteria required participants to be aged 18 years or older and able to provide informed consent. Individuals who declined participation or submitted incomplete questionnaires were excluded.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured self-administered questionnaire developed based on relevant literature and previous sexual health surveys (Muehlmann *et al.*, 2025; Castleton *et al.*, 2024). The questionnaire included sections on socio-demographic characteristics, prior experience and awareness of penile health conditions, awareness and perceptions of penile ossification, and health-seeking intentions. Participants completed the questionnaire online via a Google form. The questionnaire was pre-tested on a small sample (n=15) to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability of items, leading to minor adjustment in the questions.

Ethical Considerations: Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Respondents were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Data were stored securely and accessible only to the research team. Given the sensitive nature of sexual health topics, participants were provided with information on local sexual health resources and contacts for professional support.

Data Analysis: Completed questionnaires were checked for completeness and coded for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics, levels of awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking intentions regarding penile ossification. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were reported as means and standard deviations where appropriate. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Data visualization included tables and charts to enhance interpretability.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Young adults were the most common profile. Around 65.6% were aged 18–24, and 17.6% were ages 25–31. Participants aged 32 years or older comprised a relatively marginal cohort in the sample, suggesting that the sample was biased toward younger age groups.

In terms of marital status, 90.8% of people were single, and 6.5% were married. A small percentage of respondents were divorced or in other marital category. On educational attainment, majority of the respondents (80.8%) are in the tertiary education category, while 18.4% had secondary education; indicating a reasonably number of educated participants.

Religion was predominantly Christianity (94.3%), with minor variations of Islam (3.4%), traditional religion, and other belief systems reported. Occupationally, most survey respondents were learners (83.2%), and smaller numbers were civil servants, traders, farmers, and other workers.

Experience with Penile Health Problems

When inquired about their personal experiences regarding penile health problems, 11.5% of respondents reported having experienced such a condition, but 88.5% did not. Although there was little direct familiarity, awareness was quite high, with 73.8% of those surveyed saying that they had seen or heard about medical conditions touching the penis.

Awareness of Penile Ossification

Awareness of penile ossification was found to be on the low side. Among respondents, only 26.7% reported that they had heard about this condition. Results indicate that the concept is poorly understood among the study population.

Perceptions and Beliefs

Respondents had variable perceptions of the nature of the condition. Although 47.1% correctly reported it as not the same as being an erection, a substantial number (41.3%) were uncertain, and 11.6% reported it to be the same as being an erection. Likewise, 61.6% thought it is not common in all men, though 32.2% remained unsure.

Respondents were divided in their response on the chance of potential medical misdiagnosis, with 22.4% believing that a misdiagnosis could happen, 20.8% believing that it would not, and the remaining respondents expressed uncertainty, suggesting a lack of confidence on medical knowledge and diagnosis.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency (n=262)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18–24	172	65.6
25–31	46	17.6
≥32	44	16.8
Marital Status		
Single	238	90.8
Married	17	6.5
Divorced/Other	7	2.7
Education		
Secondary	48	18.3
Tertiary	211	80.5
Other	3	1.1
Religion		
Christianity	247	94.3
Islam	9	3.4
Traditional/Other	6	2.3
Occupation		
Student	218	83.2
Civil servant	16	6.1
Trader	10	3.8
Farmer	5	1.9
Other	13	5.0

Attitude toward Learning and Health-Seeking Behaviour

The proportion of the respondents with an interest to explore their condition was very high (86.1%). Health-seeking behaviour was highly positive: 95.0% suggested emergency hospital assessment in patients presenting with abnormal penile abnormality.

However, there was a substantial minority expressed non-biomedical interpretations or uncertainty. Although 58.7% disagreed with the notion that patients require spiritual or traditional treatment, 12.7% considered it effective and 28.5% were unsure, suggesting that a portion of respondents still adhere to cultural or spiritual beliefs.

Table 2: Experience and Awareness of Penile Health Conditions

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Experienced penile health problem	30	11.5
Never experienced penile health problem	231	88.5
Aware of general penile health issues	192	73.8
Not aware of general penile health issues	68	26.2
Heard of penile ossification	70	26.7
Never heard of penile ossification	192	73.3

Table 3: Perceptions of Penile Ossification

Statement	Correct	Incorrect	Uncertain
Penile ossification is same as erection	30 (11.6%)	107 (41.3%)	122 (47.1%)
Condition common in all men	16 (6.2%)	159 (61.6%)	83 (32.2%)
Medical misdiagnosis possible	58 (22.4%)	54 (20.8%)	147 (56.8%)

Table 4: Health-Seeking Intentions

Behavior	Frequency	Percentage
Willing to learn more	223	86.1
Recommend hospital consultation	247	95.0
Believes spiritual/traditional treatment needed	33	12.7
Rejects spiritual/traditional treatment	152	58.7
Uncertain	74	28.5

DISCUSSION

This study explored awareness, perceptions, and health-seeking intentions regarding penile ossification among predominantly young educated adults. Penile ossification in humans is extremely rare. Several reported clinical case reports and literature reviews have histologically confirmed fewer than 40 documented cases. Clinical presentation is often evident at a metaplastic level and may be associated with underlying penile pathology or trauma (Belshoff *et al.*, 2021; Arruda *et al.*). One review reported that penile ossification was most commonly associated with Peyronie's disease, but other systemic causes like diabetes mellitus, local trauma, and hyperparathyroidism have been described in sporadic cases (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2013; El Hasbani *et al.*, 2019). Because ossified plaques can form in the corpora cavernosa, penile ossification may lead to penile deviation then subsequent erectile dysfunction (Vahlensieck *et al.*, 1995).

Although penile ossification has been clinically documented, public awareness of the condition remains limited, probably due to a lack of presence in sexual health curricula or larger community-health messaging. This aligns with research highlighting gaps in sexual health educational materials and toolkits. Most available resources concentrate on general topics such as contraception and puberty with limited coverage of rarer genitourinary conditions that require a specialist focus (Castleton *et al.*, 2024). These educational gaps may partly explain the findings of the recent study, in which respondents demonstrated generally good awareness of penile health but poor knowledge of penile ossification specifically. Many respondents expressed uncertainty about whether penile ossification is similar to an erection and about its prevalence.

Similar results have been found in sexual health literacy research, indicating that young people often possess incomplete or inadequate knowledge in relation to sexual health, particularly regarding less commonly discussed or rare conditions (Muehlmann *et al.*, 2025). Systematic reviews of sexual health literacy instruments further reveal that many tools used to assess adolescent and young adult knowledge provide limited coverage of specialized topics and frequently lack adequate psychometric quality (Muehlmann *et al.*, 2025).

Nonetheless, the majority of participants expressed a strong intention to seek further information about penile ossification and acknowledged biomedical healthcare as the appropriate pathway for any abnormal penile signs. This preference for professional medical attention aligns with previous research in sexual and reproductive health, which indicates that younger individuals with higher levels of sexual health literacy are more likely to seek formal medical advice when distressed, rather than rely on informal sources of health information (Castleton *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, a minority of the participants expressed cultural or traditional interpretation, suggesting that sociocultural norms continue to influence health beliefs, even among educated populations.

Uncertainty regarding potential misdiagnosis highlights another challenge: when conditions are rare, both laypeople and healthcare providers may lack familiarity with them, potentially delaying the diagnosis and timely treatment. This underscores the importance of clear clinical communication and public education in building trust in medical diagnosis and helping individuals recognize when to seek professional care.

Overall, Both of these findings illustrate the need for sexual health education to address not only common topics but also rarer conditions such as penile ossification. Educational interventions must be evidence-informed and culturally appropriate, as gaps in formal curricula which are identified in systematic reviews of sexual health education programs may contribute to persistence of knowledge deficit among young people (Bekman *et al.*, 2023). Sexual health literacy encompasses not only general knowledge, but also awareness of specific signs, symptoms, and appropriate responses.

Conclusions

The findings indicate that although young, educated adults demonstrated high awareness of general penile health issues, specific knowledge of penile ossification remains limited. Most respondents reported openness to biomedical interventions for unusual penile conditions and expressed willingness to learn more, suggesting preparedness for targeted education initiatives. A key strength of this study is its focus on underexplored area of sexual health. By integrating both clinical and cultural perspectives, it provides data that are relevant to health communication strategies and educational programming.

Recommendations:

1. Develop evidence-based materials for use in sexual health curricula and sex education campaigns focused on uncommon penile conditions like penile ossification.

2. Address alternative health beliefs and promoting culturally sensitive and contextually relevant message that enhances acceptance of biomedical explanations.
3. Provide targeted training for primary health care providers to improve early identification, appropriate management, and referral pathways for rare penile conditions.
4. Leverage digital platforms and peer education strategies to deliver accurate and accessible information tailored to young adults.
5. Conduct further research across diverse age groups and cultural contexts to better understand variations in health awareness and associated health seeking behaviours.

Limitations

Causal inferences are limited due to the cross-sectional design of the study. The sample consisted of young, literate men who were able to complete an online Google form questionnaire, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to older adults or individuals with lower levels of education or limited internet access. Additionally, the use of self-reported data introduces the possibility of social desirability bias. Finally, the rarity of penile ossification restricts broader comparison with existing epidemiological data.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed to the various stages of this work, including its conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation, and participated in drafting the manuscript and its subsequent revisions, and read and approved the final version for publication.

